

Metaspin tensor and indices of correlation asymmetry for n -dimensional density matrices

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Abstract

The intrinsic representation of a finite-dimensional density matrix splits it, in the real orthogonal frame that diagonalizes its real part, into a diagonal block of intrinsic populations and an antisymmetric block of intrinsic coherences. The populations admit a complete hierarchical description through the indices of population asymmetry, whereas the coherence sector has so far had only a single global descriptor. We construct, in arbitrary dimension, a factorization of the intrinsic density matrix into a diagonal population factor and a population-isotropic core whose imaginary part is a real antisymmetric object, the metaspin tensor. Its skew-singular values are bounded above by unity, generalizing a bound known in three dimensions for polarization states and qutrits, and from them a nested family of indices of correlation asymmetry is built, mirroring the indices of population asymmetry. The construction reproduces the metaspin vector in three dimensions and, in higher dimensions, yields a finer classification of nonregular states, reinterpreting the known dimensional transition of nonregularity as a change in the saturation pattern of the metaspin tensor. The framework provides a real-orthogonal intrinsic hierarchical descriptor of the imaginary part of a density matrix, with applications to optical polarimetry, electromagnetic polarization matrices, and the structural analysis of quantum states in arbitrary dimension.

I. INTRODUCTION

A finite-dimensional density matrix admits, in any basis, a unique decomposition into a real symmetric part and a real antisymmetric part times the imaginary unit. The real symmetric part is positive semidefinite and admits a diagonalization by a real orthogonal change of basis; the resulting frame is called the intrinsic reference basis — intrinsic in that it is fixed by ρ itself, through its real part, with no appeal to any externally prescribed reference — and the corresponding representation is the intrinsic density matrix [1, 2]. The intrinsic representation separates the population content, encoded in the diagonal of the real part, from the correlation content, encoded in the off-diagonal of the imaginary part. This separation is geometric: it depends only on the matrix and on the absence of any preferred external basis.

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The geometric description of finite-dimensional quantum states has a long tradition centred on the generalized Bloch representation, in which a density matrix is parametrized through its expansion in a basis of Hermitian operators [3–6]. Both representations are basis dependent, and complementary structural information is exposed by each. The geometry of the qutrit state space [7–9], in particular, has been the subject of recent attention as the simplest setting in which the convex body of quantum states exhibits features absent in the qubit Bloch ball. The intrinsic representation provides a complementary viewpoint to these descriptions: instead of expanding the state in a fixed external operator basis, it adopts a state-adapted real orthogonal frame in which the real and imaginary parts of the density matrix play distinct structural roles. In this frame the imaginary part is a real antisymmetric matrix whose entries resolve the correlation content in the intrinsic reference basis, while its Frobenius norm and Youla values provide orthogonal invariants of the state.

The intrinsic population sector has been characterized hierarchically through the indices of population asymmetry [2], a nested family of $n - 1$ invariants that play, for the real symmetric part of the density matrix, a role analogous to that of the indices of purity for its eigenvalue spectrum [10]. These indices satisfy a chain of nested inequalities and provide complete decoupled information about the distribution of population imbalance across the principal axes of the intrinsic reference basis. A further property distinguishes these nested families: among the $n - 1$ descriptors that can be formed as linear combinations of the ordered eigenvalues, or of the ordered intrinsic populations, the nested construction spans a region of maximal volume, and therefore constitutes a privileged set for the detailed quantification of the corresponding deficit [10, 21, 22]. By contrast, the intrinsic correlation sector has so far been characterized only through a single global descriptor, the degree of correlation asymmetry [2], proportional to the Frobenius norm of the antisymmetric block of the intrinsic density matrix. No hierarchical description analogous to the population indices has been available for the correlation sector.

In the case of three-dimensional polarization density matrices, a more refined object is known. The metaspin vector [11] is the dimensionless vector whose components are the intrinsic correlations of the underlying population-isotropic state associated with a given density matrix; equivalently, it is the intrinsic spin vector of the state rescaled by the geometric means of the intrinsic populations. Its magnitude is bounded above by unity, and the bound is structural: it expresses the positive semidefiniteness of the underlying population-

isotropic density matrix. The construction in [11] reveals that the correlation content of a three-dimensional density matrix factors naturally into a global magnitude and an intrinsic geometric direction.

The present work develops, in arbitrary finite dimension, the natural generalization of the metaspin construction and the corresponding hierarchical description of the intrinsic correlation sector. The two main ingredients are a factorization of the intrinsic density matrix into a diagonal population factor and a population-isotropic core, and the identification of a real antisymmetric object that we call the metaspin tensor, whose skew-singular values play the role of a multicomponent magnitude bounded by unity. From these values, a nested family of indices of correlation asymmetry is constructed in direct parallel to the indices of population asymmetry. In three dimensions the metaspin tensor reduces to the antisymmetric matrix dual to the metaspin vector, and the indices of correlation asymmetry collapse to the magnitude of that vector. In dimension four and higher, the indices of correlation asymmetry distinguish states that cannot be distinguished by a single scalar descriptor; in particular, they provide a finer classification of the perfectly nonregular states characterized in [14], whose dimensional structure transition between dimension three and higher dimensions is reinterpreted as a transition in the saturation pattern of the metaspin tensor.

The scope of the construction reaches beyond polarimetry. The three-dimensional case applies indistinguishably to three-dimensional polarization states, qutrits, and three-level atomic systems [7–9]. The six-dimensional case includes electromagnetic polarization matrices, in which the joint description of the electric and magnetic field correlations of a random electromagnetic field is collected into a single 6×6 Hermitian positive semidefinite object [15]. In resource theories of imaginarity [16, 17] the imaginary part of a density matrix is the central object; in resource theories of coherence [18, 19] the imaginary part contributes to the off-diagonal structure relative to a prescribed incoherent basis. The hierarchical structure introduced here provides a real-orthogonal intrinsic decomposition of this object, intrinsic with respect to the real structure selected by $\text{Re } \rho$, that refines the scalar descriptors used in those resource theories. The framework therefore serves as structural infrastructure for the analysis of finite-dimensional density matrices in optical polarimetry, electromagnetic coherence theory, and quantum information.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II recalls the construction of the intrinsic reference basis, the indices of population asymmetry, and the existing descriptors of correlation

asymmetry, fixing the notation. Section III introduces the metaspin tensor by means of an explicit factorization of the intrinsic density matrix in the full-rank case and handles the rank-deficient case through the pseudoinverse construction familiar from three-dimensional metaspin theory. Section IV defines the indices of correlation asymmetry, establishes their nested structure, and works out the explicit forms for low dimensions. Section V analyzes the relation between the new descriptors and the existing degree of correlation asymmetry, and introduces an additional pure-correlation invariant as a dimensionless counterpart of the degree of purity restricted to the correlation sector. Section VI reinterprets the geometric nonregularity descriptor of [14] in terms of the indices of correlation asymmetry of the discriminating component and classifies perfectly nonregular states by the saturation pattern of the metaspin tensor of the discriminant. Section VII develops explicit examples in dimension three, four, five, and six. Section VIII concludes.

II. BACKGROUND AND NOTATION

A density matrix on the n -dimensional complex vector space is a Hermitian positive semidefinite operator of unit trace. Writing it in matrix form, the unique real-imaginary decomposition is

$$\rho = S + iT, \quad S = \text{Re } \rho, \quad T = \text{Im } \rho, \quad (1)$$

with S real symmetric and T real antisymmetric. The Hermiticity and positivity of ρ imply that S is real symmetric and positive semidefinite. The matrix T is real antisymmetric without further constraint beyond the positivity of ρ itself.

The intrinsic reference basis is the real orthonormal basis defined by the eigenvectors of S . Equivalently, it is the basis in which S is diagonal. The intrinsic reference basis is unique up to permutations and sign flips of its columns when the eigenvalues of S are nondegenerate; degeneracies introduce a residual orthogonal freedom in the corresponding eigenspaces. We adopt the standard convention of ordering eigenvalues in nonincreasing order and resolving column signs by demanding nonnegative leading entries; the resulting orthogonal matrix Q_O belongs to $O(n)$ and, by further fixing $\det Q_O = +1$, to $SO(n)$. Because S is real symmetric, its eigenvectors can be chosen real with respect to the representation in which ρ is written; the intrinsic reference basis is therefore the unique real orthonormal basis (modulo the residual freedom just described) in which the population structure of ρ is diagonal and

ordered, and the off-diagonal entries of iN carry the imaginary content of ρ relative to the intrinsic reference basis. The descriptors developed below are accordingly well-defined real-orthogonal-intrinsic physical functionals of the represented density matrix, computable for every ρ in any representation.

The intrinsic density matrix is the transformed object

$$\rho_O = Q_O^\top \rho Q_O = A + iN, \quad (2)$$

with $A = Q_O^\top S Q_O = \text{diag}(a_1, \dots, a_n)$, $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_n \geq 0$, $\sum_i a_i = 1$, and $N = Q_O^\top T Q_O$ real antisymmetric. We refer to the a_i as the intrinsic populations and to the off-diagonal entries N_{ij} as the intrinsic coherences. The intrinsic populations are the eigenvalues of the real symmetric part of ρ . They generally differ from the eigenvalues of ρ itself; this distinction is essential and is at the origin of the descriptors of dimensionality developed in [20]. In the language of the generalized Bloch representation, the intrinsic reference basis is the frame in which the $n(n-1)/2$ symmetric off-diagonal components of the Bloch vector vanish; the state is then carried by the $n-1$ independent diagonal components, which encode the intrinsic populations, and by the $n(n-1)/2$ antisymmetric components, which encode the intrinsic coherences, the n -dimensional counterpart of the intrinsic Stokes parameters of three-dimensional polarization optics.

The convention adopted throughout this work is $\rho_O = A + iN$, without numerical prefactor on N . In dimension three, where the antisymmetric matrix is dual via the Levi-Civita symbol to a vector with the physical interpretation of an intrinsic spin density, polarization theory commonly uses the alternative convention $\rho_O = A + (i/2)\tilde{N}$, with $\tilde{N} = 2N$, so that the spin vector is read directly from the off-diagonal entries of \tilde{N} [1, 11]. The two conventions differ by a factor of two in the antisymmetric block; the framework developed below applies uniformly under the general convention $\rho_O = A + iN$, with appropriate factor adjustments when contact is made with three-dimensional polarization theory.

A complete hierarchical description of the intrinsic population sector is provided by the indices of population asymmetry [2], defined by

$$M_k = \sum_{j=1}^k a_j - k a_{k+1}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, n-1, \quad (3)$$

which satisfy the nested inequalities $0 \leq M_1 \leq M_2 \leq \dots \leq M_{n-1} \leq 1$. They are constructed in direct analogy with the indices of purity P_k , defined from the eigenvalues of ρ [10]. Both

families provide complete hierarchical information at their respective levels: the P_k organize the spectrum of ρ , the M_k organize the spectrum of the real part of ρ in the intrinsic reference basis.

The intrinsic correlation sector has so far been characterized through a single global descriptor, the degree of correlation asymmetry [2], defined by

$$P_c^2 = 2 \|N\|_F^2 = 4 \sum_{i < j} N_{ij}^2, \quad (4)$$

proportional to the squared Frobenius norm of the antisymmetric block. The numerical value of P_c in the convention adopted here coincides with that of Ref. [2], which uses the alternative convention $\rho_O = A + (i/2)\tilde{N}$ with $\tilde{N} = 2N$ and defines $P_c^2 = \frac{1}{2}\|\tilde{N}\|_F^2$; the factor in (4) compensates the difference between the two conventions. The total degree of purity P_{nD} admits the decomposition [2]

$$P_{nD}^2 = P_p^2 + \frac{n}{2(n-1)} P_c^2, \quad (5)$$

with the degree of population asymmetry P_p written in terms of the M_k as

$$P_p^2 = \frac{n}{n-1} \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \frac{M_k^2}{k(k+1)}. \quad (6)$$

The descriptor P_c summarizes the entire correlation sector in a single number, without hierarchical structure analogous to the M_k .

In addition, two nonregularity descriptors have been introduced for density matrices. The scalar nonregularity P_N [2] is defined through the correlation-asymmetry structure of the discriminating component ρ_d of the discriminating decomposition of ρ . We summarize the latter, which underlies the application developed in Section VI. With P_k denoting the indices of purity [10], the decomposition reads [2]

$$\rho = P_1 \rho_p + (P_{n-1} - P_1) \rho_d + (1 - P_{n-1}) \frac{I_n}{n}, \quad (7)$$

where ρ_p is the rank-one projector onto the dominant eigenvector of ρ , ρ_d is a normalized discriminating state whose two largest eigenvalues coincide and whose smallest eigenvalue vanishes, and I_n/n is the maximally mixed state. The geometric nonregularity P_{Ng} [14] is defined as the normalized Frobenius norm of the excess cohesion of ρ over its dominant pure component, $\text{Im } \rho - P_1 \text{Im } \rho_p$. Both P_N and P_{Ng} vanish exactly for regular states

and reach unity for the perfectly nonregular state of the corresponding dimension. The geometric nonregularity is bounded by a dimension-dependent constant \mathcal{N}_n that takes the value $\mathcal{N}_3 = 1/(2\sqrt{2})$ in dimension three and $\mathcal{N}_n = 1/2$ for $n \geq 4$. This dimensional transition reflects a structural change in the perfectly nonregular state from a circular-plus-linear form in $n = 3$ to a doubly-coherent two-sector form in $n \geq 4$; the reinterpretation of this transition in terms of the metaspin tensor is developed in Section VI.

III. THE METASPIN TENSOR

A. Factorization in the full-rank case

Consider the intrinsic representation $\rho_O = A + iN$ of a density matrix, with $a_n > 0$, that is, with all intrinsic populations positive. Define the diagonal population factor and the population-isotropic core as

$$\Sigma_n = \sqrt{n} \operatorname{diag}(\sqrt{a_1}, \sqrt{a_2}, \dots, \sqrt{a_n}), \quad (8)$$

$$\Gamma_n = \frac{1}{n}(I_n + i\mathcal{M}_n), \quad (9)$$

where I_n is the $n \times n$ identity and \mathcal{M}_n is a real antisymmetric matrix to be determined.

Theorem 1. *There exists a unique \mathcal{M}_n such that*

$$\rho_O = \Sigma_n \Gamma_n \Sigma_n. \quad (10)$$

Equating the real and imaginary parts of (10), the real part yields

$$A = \frac{1}{n}\Sigma_n I_n \Sigma_n = \frac{1}{n}\Sigma_n^2 = \operatorname{diag}(a_1, \dots, a_n), \quad (11)$$

in agreement with the definition (8), and the imaginary part yields

$$N = \frac{1}{n}\Sigma_n \mathcal{M}_n \Sigma_n, \quad (12)$$

solved entrywise as

$$\mathcal{M}_{n,ij} = \frac{N_{ij}}{\sqrt{a_i a_j}}. \quad (13)$$

The matrix \mathcal{M}_n defined by (13) is real and antisymmetric. We refer to it as the metaspin tensor of ρ in the full-rank case. The factor $\sqrt{a_i a_j}$ is the geometric mean of the intrinsic populations associated with the i -th and j -th principal axes, and plays the role of a

normalizing standard-deviation factor in the spirit of the correlation coefficient of classical statistics [1, 11]. The metaspin tensor is the dimensionless correlation matrix obtained from the intrinsic coherences after normalization by the intrinsic populations.

B. Rank-deficient case

If some intrinsic populations vanish, let $k_n = \text{rank}(A)$ denote the true dimension of the state [20]; without loss of generality $a_1 \geq \dots \geq a_{k_n} > 0$ and $a_{k_n+1} = \dots = a_n = 0$. The positive semidefiniteness of ρ_O implies that the last $n - k_n$ rows and columns of N vanish identically. Define the diagonal pseudoinverse

$$\Sigma_n^- = \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} \text{diag}\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{a_1}}, \dots, \frac{1}{\sqrt{a_{k_n}}}, 0, \dots, 0\right), \quad (14)$$

extending the convention used in three-dimensional metaspin theory [11]. Positivity of ρ_O forces all entries of N connecting the active and inactive subspaces to vanish; hence the full problem reduces to the positive active block, where Σ_n is invertible. The metaspin tensor is then

$$\mathcal{M}_n = n \Sigma_n^- N \Sigma_n^-, \quad (15)$$

which reduces to the active $k_n \times k_n$ block computed by (13) padded by zeros. This construction makes \mathcal{M}_n well defined for any density matrix, regardless of whether the intrinsic populations are all positive or not.

C. Universal bound

The matrix $i\mathcal{M}_n$ is Hermitian. Its spectrum consists of pairs $\pm s_k$ for $k = 1, \dots, \lfloor n/2 \rfloor$ together with $n - 2\lfloor n/2 \rfloor$ zero eigenvalues, where the $s_k \geq 0$ are the skew-singular values appearing in the real Schur canonical form of \mathcal{M}_n . There exists a real orthogonal matrix $Q_{\mathcal{M}}$ such that

$$Q_{\mathcal{M}}^T \mathcal{M}_n Q_{\mathcal{M}} = \text{diag}\left(B(s_1), B(s_2), \dots, B(s_r), 0_{n-2r}\right), \quad (16)$$

with the elementary antisymmetric block $B(s)$ defined, for any real argument s , by

$$B(s) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & s \\ -s & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (17)$$

and $r = \text{rank}(\mathcal{M}_n)/2$. We call the s_k the Youla values of \mathcal{M}_n , ordered as $s_1 \geq s_2 \geq \dots \geq s_r > 0$ and extended by $s_{r+1} = \dots = s_{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} = 0$. The eigenvalues of Γ_n are then

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_k^\pm &= \frac{1 \pm s_k}{n}, \quad k = 1, \dots, r; \\ \gamma_0 &= \frac{1}{n} \text{ with multiplicity } n - 2r. \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

Theorem 2. *The Youla values of the metaspin tensor of any density matrix satisfy*

$$s_k \leq 1, \quad k = 1, \dots, \lfloor n/2 \rfloor. \tag{19}$$

The factorization (10) is a congruence transformation by Σ_n in the full-rank case, and by its pseudoinverse extension in the rank-deficient case. The positive semidefiniteness of ρ_O is therefore equivalent to the positive semidefiniteness of Γ_n on the active subspace, which by (18) yields the universal bound (19).

D. Reduction to the three-dimensional metaspin vector

For $n = 3$, the matrix \mathcal{M}_3 is a 3×3 real antisymmetric matrix, hence dual via the Levi-Civita symbol to a vector with three real components, $\mathcal{M}_{3,ij} = -\varepsilon_{ijk} \nu_k$.¹ The Youla form of \mathcal{M}_3 contains a single nontrivial 2×2 block plus a zero eigenvalue forced by the odd dimensionality, with the single Youla value $s_1 = |\boldsymbol{\nu}|$. The bound (19) reduces to $|\boldsymbol{\nu}| \leq 1$, recovering the metaspin bound of [11]. The eigenvalues of Γ_3 are $(1 + |\boldsymbol{\nu}|)/3$, $1/3$, and $(1 - |\boldsymbol{\nu}|)/3$, in agreement with Eq. (9) of [11] for the $k = 3$ case. The factorization (10) coincides with Eq. (6) of [11], with the convention difference between N and the spin vector \boldsymbol{n} (the geometric mean of intrinsic populations) absorbed in the relation between $\boldsymbol{\nu}$ and \boldsymbol{n} given by Eq. (8) of [11].

In this dimension the construction applies uniformly to three-dimensional polarization states, to qutrits as elements of the eight-dimensional state space of a three-level quantum system [7–9], and to three-level atomic and molecular systems. The metaspin vector and the indices introduced below provide a state-adapted geometric descriptor that is complementary to the generalized Bloch parametrizations standard in those contexts [6].

¹ The convention $\mathcal{M}_{3,ij} = -\varepsilon_{ijk} \nu_k$ gives the metaspin vector $\boldsymbol{\nu}$ magnitude bounded by $|\boldsymbol{\nu}| \leq 1$, consistent with the established three-dimensional metaspin theory [11]. The spin vector \boldsymbol{n} of the underlying state, dual to N in polarization theory via $N_{ij} = -\frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_{ijk} n_k$ [12, 13], is a different object: it is proportional to the electric spin angular momentum density for monochromatic fields but not in general for random polychromatic light [13].

For $n = 2$, the matrix \mathcal{M}_2 is a 2×2 real antisymmetric matrix with a single off-diagonal parameter, equal to its single Youla value. The bound (19) reduces to a single scalar bound, recovering the standard parametrization of two-dimensional density matrices in terms of the imaginary component of the Bloch vector in the intrinsic reference basis.

IV. INDICES OF CORRELATION ASYMMETRY

A. Definition and basic properties

Let $s_1 \geq s_2 \geq \dots \geq s_{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} \geq 0$ be the Youla values of the metaspin tensor \mathcal{M}_n , with the convention $s_{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor + 1} = 0$. We define the indices of correlation asymmetry by

$$C_k = \sum_{j=1}^k s_j - k s_{k+1}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, \lfloor n/2 \rfloor. \quad (20)$$

For $k = \lfloor n/2 \rfloor$, the convention $s_{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor + 1} = 0$ makes the second term vanish, giving

$$C_{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} = \sum_{j=1}^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} s_j. \quad (21)$$

The construction (20) is the direct analogue of (3) for the ordered Youla values in place of the ordered populations.

Theorem 3. *The indices of correlation asymmetry satisfy the nested inequalities*

$$0 \leq C_1 \leq C_2 \leq \dots \leq C_{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} \leq \lfloor n/2 \rfloor. \quad (22)$$

The minimum $C_k = 0$ for some $k < \lfloor n/2 \rfloor$ is attained when the first $k + 1$ Youla values coincide; the maximum $C_{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} = \lfloor n/2 \rfloor$ is attained when all Youla values saturate the bound (19) simultaneously.

The proof is a direct algebraic argument, paralleling that for the nested inequalities of the indices of population asymmetry [2] and of the indices of purity [10] with s_j in place of a_j or λ_j ; it is given in Appendix A.

B. Inversion

The Youla values are recovered from the indices of correlation asymmetry through the recurrence

$$s_k = \frac{C_k - C_{k-1}}{k} + s_{k+1}, \quad 1 \leq k \leq \lfloor n/2 \rfloor, \quad (23)$$

with the convention $C_0 = 0$ and $s_{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor + 1} = 0$. The recurrence is solved from $k = \lfloor n/2 \rfloor$ downward.

C. Cases of low dimension

For $n = 2$ and $n = 3$, $\lfloor n/2 \rfloor = 1$; there is a single Youla value $s_1 \leq 1$ and a single index of correlation asymmetry $C_1 = s_1$. In $n = 2$, C_1 coincides with the magnitude of the imaginary component of the Bloch vector in the intrinsic reference basis, and the single index exhausts the antisymmetric sector. In $n = 3$, C_1 coincides with $|\boldsymbol{\nu}|$, the magnitude of the metaspin vector of three-dimensional polarization theory [11], and equally describes the corresponding invariant of a qutrit [7–9]; the single index exhausts the orthogonal-conjugacy magnitude of the metaspin tensor, but the orientation of $\boldsymbol{\nu}$ relative to the intrinsic reference basis remains additional structural information encoded in the orthogonal matrix $Q_{\mathcal{M}}$ of the Youla frame.

For $n = 4$ and $n = 5$, $\lfloor n/2 \rfloor = 2$; there are two Youla values $s_1 \geq s_2$ and two indices $C_1 = s_1 - s_2$ and $C_2 = s_1 + s_2$. The pair (C_1, C_2) ranges over the triangular region defined by the explicit inequalities

$$C_1 \geq 0, \quad C_2 \geq C_1, \quad C_1 + C_2 \leq 2, \quad (24)$$

obtained by inverting the defining relations to $s_1 = (C_1 + C_2)/2$ and $s_2 = (C_2 - C_1)/2$ and imposing $s_1 \leq 1$ and $s_2 \geq 0$. The vertices of this region are $(0, 0)$, corresponding to vanishing intrinsic correlations; $(1, 1)$, corresponding to one Youla value saturated and the other vanishing; and $(0, 2)$, corresponding to two Youla values simultaneously saturated. The difference between $n = 4$ and $n = 5$ in this hierarchy is purely the trivial additional zero eigenvalue forced by the odd dimensionality of \mathcal{M}_5 ; the hierarchy structure is identical.

For $n = 6$, $\lfloor n/2 \rfloor = 3$; there are three Youla values and three indices $C_1 = s_1 - s_2$, $C_2 = s_1 + s_2 - 2s_3$, and $C_3 = s_1 + s_2 + s_3$. The admissible region of (C_1, C_2, C_3) is a three-dimensional polytope bounded by the inequalities (22) and the Youla bound (19) on each individual s_k .

The indices C_k are cumulative invariants in the sense that they accumulate the difference between consecutive Youla magnitudes. Unlike the indices of population asymmetry M_k , which lie in $[0, 1]$, the cumulative form admits values $C_{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} \leq \lfloor n/2 \rfloor$, so the upper index in each dimension is not restricted to unity. A per-index rescaling $\bar{C}_k = C_k/k$ brings every index

into $[0, 1]$, but it does not preserve the nested ordering (22), and a global rescaling by $\lfloor n/2 \rfloor$ introduces a dimension-dependent factor without structural gain. The cumulative form is therefore retained: beyond preserving the direct algebraic analogy with the population-asymmetry construction, it shares the extremal property of the indices of purity and of population asymmetry, in that among the nested linear descriptors of the ordered Youla values it spans a region of maximal volume [10, 21, 22], and is in this sense the privileged set for the detailed quantification of correlation asymmetry.

D. Parameter count

The intrinsic representation of a normalized density matrix involves $n^2 - 1$ independent real parameters. The orthogonal transformation Q_O that defines the intrinsic reference basis contributes $n(n - 1)/2$ parameters; the intrinsic populations contribute $n - 1$ parameters after the trace constraint; the intrinsic coherences contribute $n(n - 1)/2$ parameters. The total is

$$\frac{n(n-1)}{2} + (n - 1) + \frac{n(n-1)}{2} = n^2 - 1. \quad (25)$$

The indices of correlation asymmetry capture $\lfloor n/2 \rfloor$ of the $n(n - 1)/2$ parameters of the antisymmetric block. The remaining $n(n - 1)/2 - \lfloor n/2 \rfloor$ parameters describe the orientation of the Youla frame of \mathcal{M}_n relative to the intrinsic reference basis, encoded in the orthogonal matrix $Q_{\mathcal{M}}$ defined by (16). The indices of correlation asymmetry therefore play, for the metaspin tensor, the role of magnitudes; the matrix $Q_{\mathcal{M}}$ plays the role of an internal rotation analogous to Q_O but acting on the correlation sector. The equality $n(n - 1)/2 = \lfloor n/2 \rfloor$ holds only for $n = 2$, where the antisymmetric block has a single independent entry and the orientation degree of freedom is absent. In particular, for $n = 3$, the single Youla value s_1 gives the magnitude of the metaspin vector, while its orientation in the intrinsic reference basis supplies two additional angular parameters absorbed into $Q_{\mathcal{M}}$. For $n \geq 4$, the same distinction extends to the separation between the Youla magnitudes s_k and the orientation of the Youla frame $Q_{\mathcal{M}}$ inside the intrinsic reference basis.

The two orthogonal matrices admit a complementary reading. Q_O is the eigenframe of the population sector, while $Q_{\mathcal{M}}$ is the eigenframe of the correlation sector, the frame in which the metaspin tensor takes its Youla form. Because \mathcal{M}_n is referred to the intrinsic reference basis, $Q_{\mathcal{M}}$ is at the same time the proper rotation relating the two eigenframes, and may

be called the metaspin frame of the state. When $Q_{\mathcal{M}} = I_n$ the two frames coincide: each Youla two-plane is spanned by a pair of intrinsic reference axes, every principal coherence is carried by a pair of principal population axes, and \mathcal{M}_n is block-diagonal in the intrinsic basis — the aligned configuration of the explicit examples of Section VII. As $Q_{\mathcal{M}}$ departs from the identity the Youla two-planes tilt away from the coordinate planes of the intrinsic frame; the Youla values and the indices of correlation asymmetry are unchanged, since they are invariant under $Q_{\mathcal{M}}$, but the same magnitude content is redistributed over the population pairs, so that orientation-dependent descriptors such as P_c vary accordingly. At maximal misalignment the Youla two-planes are tilted as far as possible from every coordinate plane and a given metaspin content is spread as evenly as possible across the principal population pairs; in dimension three this is the configuration in which the metaspin vector is equally inclined to the three intrinsic axes. The relative orientation is therefore a genuine, magnitude-independent degree of freedom of the correlation sector, complementary to the indices of correlation asymmetry.

V. RELATION TO EXISTING DESCRIPTORS

A. Reexpression of the degree of correlation asymmetry

From (13), the off-diagonal entries of N are recovered as $N_{ij} = \sqrt{a_i a_j} \mathcal{M}_{n,ij}$. The squared Frobenius norm of N is therefore

$$\|N\|_F^2 = 2 \sum_{i < j} a_i a_j \mathcal{M}_{n,ij}^2, \quad (26)$$

and the degree of correlation asymmetry takes the form

$$P_c^2 = 4 \sum_{i < j} a_i a_j \mathcal{M}_{n,ij}^2. \quad (27)$$

Equation (27) expresses P_c^2 as a weighted quadratic form in the entries of \mathcal{M}_n , with weights given by the pairwise products of intrinsic populations. The descriptor P_c therefore mixes information from the metaspin tensor and the intrinsic populations, and is not a pure invariant of \mathcal{M}_n alone. In particular, P_c depends on the relative orientation of the Youla frame with respect to the intrinsic reference basis, which determines how the Youla values weigh against the principal population products.

B. The intrinsic correlation purity

We define the degree of intrinsic correlation purity as

$$P_M^2 = \frac{\|\mathcal{M}_n\|_F^2}{2\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} = \frac{1}{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} \sum_{k=1}^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} s_k^2. \quad (28)$$

The quantity P_M is a dimensionless invariant of the metaspin tensor, bounded by $0 \leq P_M \leq 1$. The lower bound is attained for states with vanishing intrinsic correlations ($\mathcal{M}_n = 0$); the upper bound is attained when all Youla values saturate (19), in which case the metaspin tensor achieves the maximal coherence structure compatible with positive semidefiniteness.

The descriptor P_M is the mean-square Youla value, in direct analogy with P_p in (6) as a mean-square index of population asymmetry. The two descriptors P_p and P_M are dimensionless counterparts of the global degree of purity restricted respectively to the population and to the correlation sectors. The two are not, however, related to P_{nD} by a quadratic identity analogous to (5); instead, the coupling enters through P_c , which contains the orientational information encoded in $Q_{\mathcal{M}}$. The notation P_M is preferred over T here to avoid collision with the imaginary part $T = \text{Im } \rho$ of the density matrix introduced in Eq. (1).

C. Three-dimensional reduction

For $n = 3$, $P_M = s_1 = |\boldsymbol{\nu}|$, and the single index of correlation asymmetry $C_1 = P_M$. The degree of correlation asymmetry P_c , by (27), is proportional to the magnitude of the spin vector of three-dimensional polarization theory, recovering the standard relation between P_c and the geometric magnitude of the intrinsic spin [1, 11]. The total degree of purity satisfies $P_{3D}^2 = P_p^2 + (3/4)P_c^2$, recovering the standard three-dimensional identity [1, 2].

D. Connection with resource theories of coherence and imaginarity

In contemporary resource-theoretic approaches, the imaginary part of a density matrix expressed in a given basis is a central object: it underlies the operational resource theory of imaginarity [16, 17] and is closely related to the off-diagonal structure of the density matrix that defines the resource theory of quantum coherence [18, 19]. In those frameworks the relevant basis is typically chosen externally (a fixed reference basis, an experimentally accessible eigenbasis, or the computational basis of a quantum-information protocol).

The framework introduced here is complementary in that the reference basis is intrinsic to the state itself. The metaspin tensor \mathcal{M}_n extracts from $\text{Im } \rho_O$ a real-orthogonal intrinsic representative whose Youla values s_k and indices C_k are invariants of the state under real-orthogonal changes of the represented real frame, intrinsic with respect to the real structure selected by $\text{Re } \rho$. A general complex unitary similarity does not preserve the real-imaginary split, so the construction is not a unitary spectral invariant; sensitivity to the choice of representation is the very feature that makes the metaspin descriptors well-defined intrinsic physical functionals of the represented density matrix, retaining structural information that any spectral or unitary-averaged label necessarily erases. The construction is therefore informative whenever the real structure is selected by the problem at hand, for instance by the spatial geometry of an optical setup or by a privileged computational basis in a finite quantum system. The hierarchical structure of the C_k therefore provides a refinement of the scalar descriptors used in those resource theories: states with the same Frobenius norm of $\text{Im } \rho$ in a given basis may have different distributions of s_k in the intrinsic frame, and the present construction makes this distribution explicit. The detailed correspondence between the C_k and operational quantifiers of imaginarity is left for separate work.

VI. APPLICATION TO NONREGULARITY

A. Geometric nonregularity in terms of the metaspin tensor of the discriminant

The geometric nonregularity descriptor $P_{Ng}^{(n)}$ [14] is defined as

$$P_{Ng}^{(n)} = \frac{\|\text{Im } \rho - P_1 \text{Im } \rho_p\|_F}{\mathcal{N}_n} = \frac{(P_{n-1} - P_1) \|\text{Im } \rho_d\|_F}{\mathcal{N}_n}, \quad (29)$$

where ρ_p is the rank-one projector onto the dominant eigenvector of ρ , P_1 and P_{n-1} are the first and last indices of purity, ρ_d is the discriminating component of the discriminating decomposition of ρ , and \mathcal{N}_n is a dimension-dependent normalization.

Let \mathcal{M}_n^d denote the metaspin tensor of ρ_d , computed by applying the construction of Section III to ρ_d . Using (26) applied to ρ_d ,

$$\|\text{Im } \rho_d\|_F^2 = 2 \sum_{i < j} a_i^d a_j^d (\mathcal{M}_{n,ij}^d)^2, \quad (30)$$

where a_i^d are the intrinsic populations of ρ_d . The normalization constant \mathcal{N}_n is determined by maximizing $\|\text{Im } \rho_d\|_F$ over the admissible discriminating states.

B. The dimensional transition revisited

The dimensional transition $\mathcal{N}_3 = 1/(2\sqrt{2})$ versus $\mathcal{N}_{n \geq 4} = 1/2$ established in [14] can now be reinterpreted as a transition in the saturation pattern of the metaspin tensor of the perfectly nonregular discriminant.

In dimension three, the perfectly nonregular discriminant has intrinsic populations $\mathbf{a}^d = (1/2, 1/4, 1/4)$. The metaspin tensor \mathcal{M}_3^d has a single nonzero Youla value s_1^d . From the explicit form of the perfectly nonregular discriminant given in Eq. (22) of [14] (in the present convention $\rho_O = A + iN$), direct computation by (13) gives $s_1^d = 1$, which saturates the bound (19). The Frobenius norm of N^d is

$$\|N^d\|_F^2 = 2a_2^d a_3^d (s_1^d)^2 = 2 \cdot \frac{1}{4} \cdot \frac{1}{4} \cdot 1 = \frac{1}{8}, \quad (31)$$

so that $\|N^d\|_F = 1/(2\sqrt{2}) = \mathcal{N}_3$. The single Youla value saturates the bound, and the constant \mathcal{N}_3 is determined by the geometric mean of the two smaller intrinsic populations of the discriminant.

In dimension four and higher, the perfectly nonregular discriminant has intrinsic populations $\mathbf{a}^d = (1/4, 1/4, 1/4, 1/4)$ (followed by zeros if $n > 4$). The metaspin tensor is given by $\mathcal{M}_n^d = 4N^d$, and direct computation by (13) using the form of ρ_d given in Eq. (26) of [14] reveals two Youla values $s_1^d = s_2^d = 1$, both saturating the bound. The Frobenius norm of N^d is

$$\|N^d\|_F^2 = 2 \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^2 [(s_1^d)^2 + (s_2^d)^2] = 2 \cdot \frac{1}{16} \cdot 2 = \frac{1}{4}, \quad (32)$$

so that $\|N^d\|_F = 1/2 = \mathcal{N}_n$ for $n \geq 4$. The ratio $\mathcal{N}_{n \geq 4}/\mathcal{N}_3 = \sqrt{2}$ is the square root of the number of simultaneously saturating Youla values. This identification holds because in both maximizing discriminants the active pair weights $a_i^d a_j^d$ are equal in the relevant blocks, so that the increase from one to two simultaneously saturated metaspin pairs multiplies the squared cohesion by two. For the simplifications $\|N^d\|_F^2 = 2a_i^d a_j^d (s_k^d)^2$ used above, the Youla frame $Q_{\mathcal{M}}$ of \mathcal{M}_n^d aligns with the intrinsic reference basis on the active blocks; in general, the translation from the Frobenius norm of N to the Youla magnitudes s_k requires the orthogonal rotation $Q_{\mathcal{M}}$ defined by (16).

C. Saturation patterns of the discriminant metaspin tensor

The metaspin hierarchy refines the classification of nonregular discriminants. The geometrically perfect nonregular discriminant in dimension $n \geq 4$, in the sense of the maximum discriminant cohesion $\|\text{Im } \rho_d\|_F = \mathcal{N}_{n \geq 4} = 1/2$ established in [14], corresponds uniquely to the configuration with two simultaneously saturated Youla values. Other saturation patterns of \mathcal{M}_n^d are structurally meaningful and are distinguished by the metaspin hierarchy, but they lie strictly below the maximum discriminant cohesion and do not realize the geometrically perfect nonregular state of the corresponding dimension.

In dimension four, the doubly-coherent configuration has $s_1^d = s_2^d = 1$ and indices of correlation asymmetry $(C_1^d, C_2^d) = (0, 2)$; it corresponds to the form analyzed in [14] and realizes the universal upper bound $\|\text{Im } \rho_d\|_F = \mathcal{N}_4 = 1/2$. A single-pair dominated configuration has $s_1^d = 1$ and $s_2^d < 1$, with indices $(C_1^d, C_2^d) = (1 - s_2^d, 1 + s_2^d)$. Single-pair dominated discriminants are structurally important because they saturate one metaspin pair and are distinguished by the metaspin hierarchy, but they do not saturate the maximum discriminant cohesion unless the required second coherent sector is also present. Such configurations may nevertheless exhibit equal scalar nonregularity when measured by the correlation-asymmetry construction of [2] alone.

In dimension five and higher, configurations with up to $\lfloor n/2 \rfloor$ simultaneously saturating Youla values are admissible, distinguished by the patterns of the indices of correlation asymmetry. Single-pair, double-pair, and higher-pair coherent states are all structurally distinguished by the metaspin hierarchy. For $n \geq 6$, configurations exist where the saturation is fractional (some $s_k^d < 1$) and partial (some $s_k^d = 0$ and others not), giving a richer taxonomy of nonregular discriminants than is available in dimension three or four. Only the configurations with two simultaneously saturated Youla values realize the geometrically perfect nonregular state of the discriminant cohesion in $n \geq 4$.

D. Refinement of the scalar nonregularity

The scalar nonregularity P_N of [2] is defined through the correlation-asymmetry structure of ρ_d . In dimension $n \geq 4$, the metaspin tensor framework allows distinguishing states with the same P_N by reading off the full hierarchy of indices of correlation asymmetry

$(C_1^d, \dots, C_{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor}^d)$ of the discriminant. This refinement is structurally analogous to the refinement provided by the indices of purity over the scalar degree of purity: a single number is replaced by a hierarchical vector that captures the distribution of nonregularity content across the principal pairs.

VII. EXAMPLES

A. Three-dimensional polarization states and qutrits

For $n = 3$, the construction reduces to the three-dimensional metaspin theory of [11]. The metaspin vector $\boldsymbol{\nu}$ is recovered from \mathcal{M}_3 by Hodge duality, and the single index of correlation asymmetry C_1 coincides with $|\boldsymbol{\nu}|$. The Frobenius norm of N is

$$\|N\|_F^2 = 2(a_1 a_2 \nu_3^2 + a_1 a_3 \nu_2^2 + a_2 a_3 \nu_1^2), \quad (33)$$

which, after the convention relation between N and the spin vector \mathbf{n} of the field [12, 13], recovers Eq. (8) of [11]. The degree of correlation asymmetry P_c corresponds to the magnitude of the intrinsic spin vector, and depends on both $|\boldsymbol{\nu}|$ and on the orientation of $\boldsymbol{\nu}$ relative to the intrinsic reference basis. The pure-correlation invariant $P_M = |\boldsymbol{\nu}|$ is independent of this orientation.

The same construction applies, without modification, to a qutrit (a generic three-level quantum system). The geometry of qutrit state space has been the subject of detailed investigations [7–9] that emphasize the eight-dimensional structure of the convex body of qutrit states and its non-Bloch-ball character. The intrinsic representation does not parametrize this convex body globally; instead, it provides, for each state, an adapted real orthogonal frame in which the imaginary part of the density matrix admits a single scalar magnitude $|\boldsymbol{\nu}|$ bounded by unity. The two descriptions are complementary: external parametrizations yield a fixed coordinate system in which the convex body is described, whereas the intrinsic description yields, at each state, the natural decomposition into population and correlation sectors.

B. Four-dimensional structures

For $n = 4$, two qualitatively distinct structures occur. We illustrate them with intrinsic density matrices normalized for clarity.

As a first example, consider the intrinsic density matrix

$$\rho_O = \frac{1}{4}(I_4 + i \operatorname{diag}(B(1), B(1))), \quad (34)$$

with $B(1) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$. The intrinsic populations are $a_i = 1/4$ for all i , $\Sigma_4 = I_4$, and the metaspin tensor is $\mathcal{M}_4 = \operatorname{diag}(B(1), B(1))$. The two Youla values are $s_1 = s_2 = 1$, both saturating the bound (19); the configuration is therefore doubly coherent. The indices of correlation asymmetry are $C_1 = 0$ and $C_2 = 2$. The state is the perfectly nonregular state of dimension four in the sense of [14]. The eigenvalues of ρ_O are $1/2$ and 0 , each with multiplicity two.

As a second, structurally distinct example, consider the intrinsic density matrix

$$\rho_O = \frac{1}{4}(I_4 + i \operatorname{diag}(B(1), B(0))), \quad (35)$$

with the same population structure. The Youla values are $s_1 = 1$, $s_2 = 0$, and the indices of correlation asymmetry are $C_1 = 1$, $C_2 = 1$; the configuration is single-pair dominated. The state is structurally distinct from (34) despite both having $C_2 \geq 1$: in (34) the cohesion is distributed equally between two coherent pairs, in (35) it is concentrated in a single pair. The eigenvalues of ρ_O are $1/2$, $1/4$, $1/4$, and 0 .

The two states (34) and (35) are both discriminants with maximally saturated principal Youla pair, but only (34) realizes the maximum discriminant cohesion at the universal upper bound $\|\operatorname{Im} \rho_O\|_F = \mathcal{N}_4 = 1/2$, while (35) sits strictly below this bound, $\|\operatorname{Im} \rho_O\|_F = 1/(2\sqrt{2}) = \mathcal{N}_3$. The pair (C_1, C_2) distinguishes the two configurations directly.

C. Five-dimensional case

For $n = 5$, the antisymmetric matrix \mathcal{M}_5 has at most rank four, since odd-dimensional real antisymmetric matrices have at least one zero eigenvalue. The Youla form contains at most two 2×2 blocks plus an additional zero, and the indices of correlation asymmetry have

the same triangular structure as in $n = 4$, namely $C_1 = s_1 - s_2$ and $C_2 = s_1 + s_2$. As a concrete illustration, consider the intrinsic density matrix

$$\rho_O = \frac{1}{5} (I_5 + i \text{diag}(B(1), B(\frac{1}{2}), 0)), \quad (36)$$

with $a_i = 1/5$ for all i , $\Sigma_5 = I_5$, and metaspin tensor $\mathcal{M}_5 = \text{diag}(B(1), B(1/2), 0)$. The Youla values are $s_1 = 1$, $s_2 = 1/2$; the indices of correlation asymmetry are $C_1 = 1/2$ and $C_2 = 3/2$; the intrinsic correlation purity is $P_M = \sqrt{(1 + 1/4)/2} = \sqrt{5}/\sqrt{8}$. The phenomenology of saturation patterns established in dimension four extends directly; five-dimensional density matrices arise in the description of five-level quantum systems, characterized by the same indices of correlation asymmetry as in dimension four.

D. Six-dimensional case and electromagnetic polarization matrices

For $n = 6$, the metaspin tensor admits three Youla values $s_1 \geq s_2 \geq s_3$ and three indices of correlation asymmetry $C_1 = s_1 - s_2$, $C_2 = s_1 + s_2 - 2s_3$, and $C_3 = s_1 + s_2 + s_3$. This dimension is relevant to 6×6 electromagnetic polarization matrices [15], where the 6×6 representation collects the electric and magnetic field correlations and their cross components into a single Hermitian positive semidefinite object.

The metaspin tensor of a 6×6 electromagnetic polarization matrix is a real antisymmetric 6×6 matrix whose entries can be partitioned according to the natural block structure of the underlying field, into electric-electric, magnetic-magnetic, and electric-magnetic components. The three Youla values capture the magnitude of correlation along three principal coherence directions of the combined electromagnetic field. The indices of correlation asymmetry organize these magnitudes into the hierarchical descriptor structurally identical to the indices of correlation asymmetry of any other six-dimensional density matrix. The translation between the indices of correlation asymmetry of the full 6×6 matrix and the four-channel decomposition of the electric-magnetic cross-correlation block introduced in [15] depends on the relative orientation of the intrinsic reference basis and the natural electric-magnetic block structure. The detailed development of this correspondence is left for separate work.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

We have developed a hierarchical description of the intrinsic correlation sector of a finite-dimensional density matrix that parallels the existing hierarchical description of the intrinsic population sector. The central object is the metaspin tensor \mathcal{M}_n , a real antisymmetric matrix obtained as the imaginary part of the population-isotropic core Γ_n in the factorization $\rho_O = \Sigma_n \Gamma_n \Sigma_n$ of the intrinsic density matrix, in which the diagonal factor Σ_n carries the intrinsic populations and the core Γ_n carries the population-normalized correlation structure. The Youla values of \mathcal{M}_n are bounded above by unity by a universal positivity argument, and the indices of correlation asymmetry constructed from these values satisfy nested inequalities directly analogous to the indices of population asymmetry.

In dimension three the construction reduces to the metaspin vector of three-dimensional polarization theory, and applies, without modification, to qutrits and three-level atomic systems. In dimension four and higher the construction provides a refinement that distinguishes states which the existing scalar correlation descriptors do not distinguish. The dimensional transition observed in the geometric nonregularity descriptor between dimension three and four admits a clean reinterpretation as a transition in the number of simultaneously saturating Youla values of the metaspin tensor of the discriminating component, with the ratio $\mathcal{N}_{n \geq 4} / \mathcal{N}_3 = \sqrt{2}$ identified as the square root of this number.

The construction completes the rotation-invariant magnitude hierarchy of the intrinsic correlation sector. Together with the intrinsic populations and their indices of population asymmetry, and the orientational information encoded in the orthogonal matrix Q_O of the intrinsic reference basis and in the orthogonal matrix $Q_{\mathcal{M}}$ of the Youla frame, the indices of correlation asymmetry exhaust the rotation-invariant magnitude content of the density matrix. The two hierarchies of indices, one for populations and one for correlations, are conceptually parallel and structurally identical, providing a unified language for the structural analysis of density matrices across dimensions.

Several extensions follow naturally. The relative orientation between the intrinsic reference basis and the Youla frame of the metaspin tensor constitutes structural information not captured by either hierarchy of indices alone; beyond the geometric role described in Section IV, its physical interpretation in the contexts of optical polarimetry and quantum information remains open. The application to the geometric nonregularity descriptor ad-

mits refinement through index-based classification of nonregular states, with consequences for dimensions five and higher that have not been previously analyzed. The extension to representations of structured objects such as electromagnetic polarization matrices connects the present framework to recent developments in the joint electric-magnetic description of random electromagnetic fields. In a complementary direction, the framework provides notational and conceptual infrastructure for analyses of finite-dimensional density matrices in quantum information, where the imaginary part is central in resource theories of imaginarity [16, 17] and contributes to the off-diagonal structure studied in resource theories of coherence [18, 19], and in foundational analyses of the role of complex versus real structure in quantum mechanics. The application of the metaspin tensor and the indices of correlation asymmetry to these contexts will be developed in separate work.

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Appendix A: Proof of the nested inequalities

We prove Theorem 3 explicitly. The inequality $C_k \leq C_{k+1}$ for $1 \leq k \leq \lfloor n/2 \rfloor - 1$ is equivalent to

$$\sum_{j=1}^k s_j - k s_{k+1} \leq \sum_{j=1}^{k+1} s_j - (k+1) s_{k+2}. \quad (\text{A1})$$

Subtracting the left-hand side from the right-hand side gives

$$s_{k+1} + k s_{k+1} - (k+1) s_{k+2} = (k+1)(s_{k+1} - s_{k+2}), \quad (\text{A2})$$

which is nonnegative by the ordering $s_{k+1} \geq s_{k+2}$. The lower bound $C_1 \geq 0$ follows from $C_1 = s_1 - s_2$ with $s_1 \geq s_2 \geq 0$.

For the upper bound $C_{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} \leq \lfloor n/2 \rfloor$, we use $s_j \leq 1$ from Theorem 2 in the sum

$$C_{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} = \sum_{j=1}^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} s_j \leq \lfloor n/2 \rfloor. \quad (\text{A3})$$

The saturation conditions follow by inspection of the bounds.

Appendix B: Rank-deficient case in detail

When some intrinsic populations vanish, the factorization (10) requires the pseudoinverse construction described in Section III B. Let $k_n = \text{rank}(A)$ and let P_{k_n} denote the orthogonal projector onto the span of the first k_n coordinate axes (the active subspace). The positivity of ρ_O implies $P_{k_n} N P_{k_n}^\perp = 0$ and $P_{k_n}^\perp N P_{k_n}^\perp = 0$, where $P_{k_n}^\perp = I_n - P_{k_n}$.

On the active subspace, the construction (13) applies directly with $a_i, a_j > 0$ for $i, j \leq k_n$. The resulting metaspin tensor \mathcal{M}_n has support on the active subspace and Youla form

$$Q_{\mathcal{M}}^\top \mathcal{M}_n Q_{\mathcal{M}} = \text{diag} (B(s_1), \dots, B(s_{r'}), 0_{n-2r'}), \quad (\text{B1})$$

with $r' \leq \lfloor k_n/2 \rfloor$ and the orthogonal matrix $Q_{\mathcal{M}}$ acting trivially on the inactive subspace. The Youla values s_k satisfy the same bound (19), and the $\lfloor n/2 \rfloor$ indices of correlation asymmetry are defined by (20) using $\lfloor n/2 \rfloor$ in place of $\lfloor k_n/2 \rfloor$, or equivalently using s_k with the convention that the additional values s_k for $\lfloor k_n/2 \rfloor < k \leq \lfloor n/2 \rfloor$ are zero. The formal definition (20) therefore extends uniformly.

The cases of low rank are particularly transparent. A rank-one state (pure state of true dimension one) has $a_1 = 1$ and $a_i = 0$ for $i \geq 2$, hence $\mathcal{M}_n = 0$ and all indices of correlation asymmetry vanish. A rank-two state (linear or two-dimensional polarization in three-dimensional language) has at most one nonzero Youla value, and the structure reduces to a single $C_1 \leq 1$. The general case interpolates between these limits and the full-rank case considered in Section III A.

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